

RADIOGRAPHY OF THE FEMALE ENTREPRENEURIAL ENVIRONMENT IN ROMANIA FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF BARRIERS AND SOCIAL AND GOVERNMENTAL SUPPORT

Author(s)*: Alexandra NĂSTĂSOIU¹, Laura BACALI², Ancuta Nicoleta NASTAI (REMETE)³,
Monica BOGDAN⁴

Position: PhD Student¹, Prof., PhD, Ing., Ec.², PhD Student³, S.I., PhD., ec.⁴

University: Technical University of Cluj-Napoca

Address: Cluj-Napoca, Muncii, Str., No. 103-105, Romania

Email: ainastasioiu@yahoo.ro ¹, laura.bacali@mis.utcluj.ro ², ancuta.nastai@mis.utcluj.ro ³,
monica.turcu@mis.utcluj.ro⁴.

Webpage: <http://www.utcluj.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose – *The study aims to make a radiography of the female entrepreneurial environment in Romania taking into account on the one hand the barriers faced by women entrepreneurs, and on the other hand the adequate support provided by society and authorities.*

Methodology/approach – *In order to identify the perception of women entrepreneurs in Romania regarding the entrepreneurial environment, we used empirical research based on the survey method, and the questionnaire as a working tool.*

Findings – *The favorable basic element that characterizes the female entrepreneurial environment in Romania is represented by the existence of an equality of gender opportunities and at the opposite pole is the acces to financing sources.*

Research limitations/implications - *The most important limitation of this study is the sampling method and its size. It would be interesting to extend the study at European or global level.*

Practical implications – *The identification of barriers is the basis of solutions that can come from the government or civil society*

Originality/value – *Analysis of the barriers compared to the support from civil society and the government from Romania.*

Key words: *entrepreneurship, government support, civil society.*

Introduction

Female entrepreneurship is an important factor for the economic development of a state. However, the Mastercard Index of Women Entrepreneurs 2018 shows that the number of women entrepreneurs is not always linked to the wealth and economic development of states' economies as a high rate of women entrepreneurs is registered in less rich markets.

The cause of this situation comes from the need to survive. This situation includes states such as Ghana, Uganda, Bangladesh and Vietnam.

In developed countries (New Zealand, Sweden, Canada, the United States, Belgium) women create businesses because of existing opportunities. In these countries, women tend to have access to greater resources and receive support to continue their entrepreneurial project.

In order to achieve real economic development, it is not only the number of women entrepreneurs that matters, but it is necessary for the businesses built by women to survive, to have a favorable environment for women entrepreneurs.

The basis for creating a favorable environment for women entrepreneurs is the attitude towards working women and gender equality, aspects which affects the economic participation of women and entrepreneurship everywhere.

At the level of the Romanian state, there is a satisfactory equality between women and men, as shown in the report Female Entrepreneurship Index in 2015, which states that the indicator with the highest score has equal rights between women and men. From then until now the situation has remained constant.

According to the MASTERCARD INDEX OF WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS 2021 90 percent of women who lost jobs during COVID-19 did not return to work, 64 percent of women -led firms have been strongly impacted by the pandemic and 80 pecercent of women- owned businesses with credit needs are either unserved or underserved.

In addition, it is shown in the Mastercard Index that women entrepreneurs represent 37 percent of global GDP and have been more severely affected by the pandemic and face continued barriers to reaching their full potential. COVID-19 has had a negative effect on women, adding another 36 years to the estimated time it will take to close the global gender gap on economic, opportunity, education, political power and health.

Index-ul 2021 ranks Romania among the countries where women's advancement tends to be hampered by less supportive entrepreneurial conditions (Romania ranks 44th out of 65 countries)

Global economic recovery depends on investing in women entrepreneurs it is an integrated declaration at the global, european and national level. This requires a specific approach to the subject from a diverse perspective. We propose the approach based on three key points: specific barriers - governmental support and civic support.

Barriers to the development of a business by women entrepreneurs

The obstacles that women entrepreneurs face can be grouped as follows: economic barriers, contextual barriers and software barriers.

Economic barriers are related to the fact that women entrepreneurs find it more difficult to access sources of funding compared to men. This situation is even more evident in the science and technology sector, as this sector most often requires substantial investment.

Contextual obstacles refer to women's educational choices, technology, science and inventions.

Software barriers are related to the lack of access to the right networks. These also include the lack of necessary entrepreneurial skills, such as confidence, assertiveness and risk-taking, as well as the lack of models to send a positive message to women entrepreneurs.

Financial support from the government, especially in terms of start-up capital, is an important factor in motivating women to set up their own businesses.

Financing is one of the most important and difficult challenges for setting up, running, innovating, expanding and developing a business. This obstacle stems from a lack of investor confidence, as women-run businesses are perceived as risky, making it more difficult for women entrepreneurs to obtain financing.

There is no unitary view of the gap mechanism. Various explanations have been put forward to explain this situation, one of which is that the variations observed between women and men are the direct result of the biased behavior of investors who choose to provide capital disproportionately and rather to male entrepreneurs.

Another explanation argues that the gender difference in how capital is allocated is caused by the behavior of women entrepreneurs who seek and therefore receive less capital for their businesses (Kanze et al., 2018a).

Lately, this situation is explained by the fact that women are more likely to be associated with companies with less capital, less risk tolerance and therefore less desirable for the type of financial capital needed to finance a certain level of growth. (Kanze et al., 2018b)

Results of the study We ask Men to win & Women Not to Lose (Kanze et al., 2018c) reveal an important distinction in the types of questions of investors addressed to entrepreneurs, which explain the

disparities in their financing decisions. This distinction places entrepreneurs in two positions: women entrepreneurs as playing not to lose, while male entrepreneurs as playing to win, perpetuating the gender gap.

A possible explanation for the poor performance can be given by social expectations. Women entrepreneurs are expected to play the role of mother or caregiver.

Sources of support

Ensuring gender equality between women and men was an important element for the policies and legislation of the Romanian state.

In Romania there are several institutions involved in gender equality, such as: the National Agency for Equal Opportunities between Women and Men, the National Council Against Discrimination, the National Commission for Equal Opportunities between Women and Men (CONES).

In addition to the theoretical part of entrepreneurship, in Romania by *Order no. 3262/2017 of 16 February 2017*, was intended the organization and functioning of student entrepreneurial societies, called SAS, in order to provide a mechanism to support, develop and encourage entrepreneurship in the university environment, by providing complementary services and assistance in higher education.

Along with government initiatives, civil society became involved in supporting women entrepreneurs to develop and promote female entrepreneurship.

Over time, women in Romania have had access to various programs organized by the European Commission and the government to benefit from funding for their entrepreneurial project.

Research material and method

Participants

The sample consists of 39 women entrepreneurs ($n = 39$), who own businesses in several occupational fields, aged between 18 and over 65 years ($m = 2.85$; $S = .844$). The majority (92.3 percent) of female entrepreneurs run businesses that have less than 9 employees ($m = 1.15$; $S = 0.67$). Most subjects have undergraduate and postgraduate studies ($m = 5.90$; $S = 1.23$).

Research tools

The survey method was used in the research activity and the questionnaire as a working tool. For the purpose of the investigation, which is the object of this research, a questionnaire was developed aimed at conducting an empirical research, to highlight the relevant aspects related to the experience of women entrepreneurs in several cities in Romania.

The pre-testing of the questionnaire was carried out on a sample of 10 subjects, who were not subsequently included in the final sample. Following the pre-test, the necessary changes were made and the questionnaire was drafted in the final form.

Design and specification of the model

The present study is a descriptive, non-experimental, cross-sectional one, which aims to evaluate the entrepreneurial environment of women.

The research is exploratory, quantitative, unrepresentative, without the possibility of extrapolating the results to the entire population.

In order to obtain the data, we used a non-random sampling method, both in the form of snowballs and on the basis of accessibility.

Results

The data were analyzed descriptively, according to the descriptive statistics generated by the Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) software.

According to the table 1, most subjects (43.6percent) agree that it is a difficult process to start a business in Romania, and 23.1 percent of them totally agree with this statement.

Table 1. Summary of answers to questions. The frequency of response is expressed in the form of numbers (percentage).

	<u>Women entrepreneur</u> n=39
Item description	
Starting a business was a difficult process:	
Total agreement; Agreement; Indifferent; Disagreement; Total disagreement	9(23.1); 17(43.6); 5(12.8); 5(12.8); 3(7.7)
The bureaucratic aspects of running a business are not difficult:	
Total agreement; Agreement; Indifferent; Disagreement; Total disagreement	6(15.4); 7(17.9); 4(10.3); 13(33.3); 9(23.1)
It was difficult to identify a source (s) of funding:	
Total agreement; Agreement; Indifferent; Disagreement; Total disagreement	13(33.3); 18(46.2); 1(2.6); 5(12.8); 2(5.1)
It is difficult to keep the right employees:	
Total agreement; Agreement; Indifferent; Disagreement; Total disagreement	15(38.5); 13(33.3); 4(10.3); 4(10.3); 3(7.7)
Women have the same business opportunities as men:	
Total agreement; Agreement; Indifferent; Disagreement; Total disagreement	11(28.2); 15(38.5); 3(7.7); 7(17.9); 3(7.7)
A woman needs to put in more effort compared to a man when she wants to grow a business:	
Total agreement; Agreement; Indifferent; Disagreement; Total disagreement	6(15.4); 9(23.1); 7(17.9); 11(28.2); 6(15.4)
In Romania, female entrepreneurship is supported and encouraged:	
Total agreement; Agreement; Indifferent; Disagreement; Total disagreement	3(7.7); 11(28.2); 15(38.5); 8(20.5); 2(5.1)
The society offers the same confidence to women entrepreneurs as men entrepreneurs:	
Total agreement; Agreement; Indifferent; Disagreement; Total disagreement	3(7.7); 17(43.6); 9(23.1); 8(20.5); 2(5.1)
Investors are more willing to invest in start-up led by women:	
Total agreement; Agreement; Indifferent; Disagreement; Total disagreement	2(5.1); 6(15.4); 17(43.6); 13(33.3); 1(2.6)
The ambiance of the company's environment perceived by customers:	
Very good; Good; Average; Low; Very low	20(51.3); 18(46.2); 1(2.6); 0(0); 0(0)
The image of the company perceived by customers:	
Very good; Good; Average; Low; Very low	20(51.3); 15(38.5); 4(10.3); 0(0); 0(0)
Do you consider that in Romania, female entrepreneurship benefits from adequate support from the authorities?	
No; Yes; I do not know	9(23.1); 12(30.8); 18(46.2)
Do you consider that professional training is an important factor in the success of a business in female entrepreneurship?	
No; Yes; I do not know	5(12.8); 32(82.1); 2(5.1)
How do you assess the legislative environment in the U.E. relative to female entrepreneurship?	
Very favorable; Favorable; Neutral; Unfavorable; Very unfavorable	1(2.6); 11(28.2); 24(61.5); 1(2.6); 2(5.1)

Regarding the difficulty of the bureaucratic aspects related to the functioning of a business, 56.4 percent of the respondents consider that these aspects impose difficulties in Romania.

Many of the respondents (46.2 percent) agree that it is difficult to identify funding sources, and 33.3 percent of women entrepreneurs fully agree with this. 38.5 percent of women entrepreneurs totally agree that it is difficult to maintain the right employees, and 33.3 percent agree.

The majority of women entrepreneurs (66.7 percent) who took part in this study believe that women have the same business opportunities as men. Thus, it is not at all surprising that 43.6 percent of the subjects consider that women should not make more effort than men when they want to develop a business, and 17.9 percent have an indifferent position about this statement.

Most of the respondents (38.5 percent) maintain an indifferent position towards the statement by which female entrepreneurship is encouraged and supported in Romania, while 28.2 percent agree with this statement.

Also, 51.3 percent of the participants in the study believe that the company offers the same trust to women entrepreneurs as it offers men to entrepreneurs.

Investors are more willing to invest in women-led start-ups, it does not seem to be a statement to convince respondents, most of them (43.6 percent) have an indifferent position, and 33.3 percent are in disagree with this.

Women entrepreneurs believe that customers have a very good (51.3 percent) and good (46.2 percent) perception of the environment of their business.

Regarding the image of the company that the study participants own, 51.5 percent consider that it is very good, and 38.5 percent of them consider that the image of the owned company is a good one.

The majority of respondents (46.2 percent) do not know whether in Romania female entrepreneurship benefits from adequate support from the authorities, while 30.8 percent consider that female entrepreneurship is supported by the authorities.

Also, the respondents (82.1percent) consider that the professional training is an important factor of the success of a business in female entrepreneurship.

The legislative environment in the European Union (EU) is considered neutral by the vast majority (61.5 percent) of the subjects, and 28.2 percent consider it favorable.

Next, we aim to see if there are differences in perception regarding the effort that a woman must make compared to a man when she wants to develop a business, and in achieving this goal we will use statistical analysis χ^2 .

H_0 = The effort that a woman has to make is equal to the effort that a man has to make when he wants to develop a business.

H_1 = A woman has to put in more effort compared to a man when she wants to start a business.

A chi-square goodness of fit test was used (Figure 1) to test whether the pattern of the effort made between men and women when they want to develop a business differed from randomness. Expected frequencies in all cells were greater than five. Total agreement regarding a greater effort on the part of women (6), agree on a greater effort on the part of women (9), indifference in terms of greater effort on the part of women (7), disagreement regarding a greater effort on the part of women (11), total disagreement regarding a greater effort on the part of women (6), are not statistically significantly different, $\chi^2(4, n39)=2.41$, $p= 0,66$, indicating that there is no difference between the effort that a woman has to make and the effort that a man has to make when he wants to develop a business.

Figure 1. Perception regarding the effort that a woman has to make compared to a man.

At the same time, we are interested to see to what extent there is an association relationship between the business opportunities that men and women have, respectively the trust that society gives to women and men entrepreneurs. In this direction we made a Pearson correlation between these two variables (Figure 2).

Figure 2 shows that there is a moderately positive correlation ($r = 0.54$), statistically significant ($p = 1.0$), between offering the same business opportunities to both women and men (independent variable) and offering confidence to women entrepreneurs and men entrepreneurs (dependent variable).

Figure 2. Scatter Plot of “The society offers the same confidence to women entrepreneurs as men” by “Women have the same business opportunities as men”.

We are also interested in seeing the respondents' perception depending on their age, on the difficulty of the process of starting a business. To achieve this we resorted to analysis by groups.

After analyzing the data, we can see (Table 2) that 81.3 percent of respondents aged 18-35, agree that starting a business is a difficult process.

Table 2. The difficulty of starting a business by age categories

Age	Frequency	Percent
18-35 Valid	total agreement	5 31.3
	agreement	8 50.0
	indifferent	2 12.5
	total disagreement	1 6.3
	Total	16 100.0
35-45 Valid	total agreement	2 14.3
	agreement	6 42.9
	indifferent	2 14.3
	disagreement	3 21.4
	total disagreement	1 7.1
Total	14 100.0	
45-65 Valid	total agreement	2 25.0
	agreement	3 37.5
	disagreement	2 25.0
	total disagreement	1 12.5
	Total	8 100.0
>65 Valid	indifferent	1 100.0

The agreement regarding the difficulty of starting a business, is in a percentage of 42.9 percent in the age category 35-45 years, and in the same age category 21.4 percent show their disagreement with this statement.

Subjects belonging to the age category 45-65 years in proportion of 37.5 percent agree with the fact that starting a business is a difficult process, and in an equal percentage of 25 percent they totally agree.

Discussion and conclusions

As it results from the study, most respondents have less than 9 employees from which we can deduce a smaller size of the entrepreneurial project. Therefore, an aspect of theoretical interest with practical results could be to identify the reasons for the smaller size of the business and to identify solutions for the development of women-led companies.

For female entrepreneurship to contribute to the economic development of a state, it is not enough to have a large number of women entrepreneurs, but it is necessary to create conditions for building an environment conducive to the development of female entrepreneurship. Based on this idea, we noticed that a favorable environment for women entrepreneurs involves identifying barriers and providing appropriate solutions, providing adequate support from both government and society.

The research carried out confirms Romania's favorable position regarding ensuring equal rights between women and men, as most women entrepreneurs participating in the study consider that they have the same business opportunities as men. Also, the majority of respondents consider that the company gives them a similar trust to that of men and they enjoy a very good perception of the company's image. With this favorable basis, it is important to build appropriate solutions to overcome other obstacles, such as access to finance, attracting investors, given that in terms of support from the authorities, only about a third of women entrepreneurs believe that there is adequate support from the authorities.

Understanding the barriers specific to women entrepreneurs will be a central point for supporting and recovering the post-pandemic economy.

Notes

**ACKNOWLEDGMENT:* This paper was financially supported by the Project "Entrepreneurial competences and excellence research in doctoral and postdoctoral programs - ANTREDOC", project co-funded by the European Social Fund financing agreement no. 56437/24.07.2019.

References

Ana, B. C.

2019

Women's entrepreneurship, the 21st century challenge for a better world. *Annals of Constantin Brancu-si'University of Targu-Jiu. Economy Series*, (6).

Bartel, C. A., A. Wrzesniewski, and B. Wiesenfeld

2021

The struggle to establish organizational membership and identification in remote work contexts" In C. A. Bartel, S. Blader, and A. Wrzesniewski (eds.), *Identity and the Modern Organization*: 119-133. Mahwah, NJ: LEA.

Burt, R. S.

2020

"The network structure of social capital." In B. M. Staw and R. I. Sutton (eds.), *Research in Organizational Behavior*, 22: 345-423. New York: Elsevier.

Card, M.

2018

Mastercard Index of Women Entrepreneurs (MIWE) 2018.

Cowling, M.

2010

Entrepreneurship, gender and job creation: European dynamics. *Women Entrepreneurs and the Global Environment for Growth: A Research Perspective*, 19

Chowdhury, T. Y., Yeasmin, A., & Ahmed, Z.

2018

Perception of women entrepreneurs to accessing bank credit. *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*, 8(1), 1-16.

Daley, J.

2013

Are entrepreneurs born or made. *Entrepreneur*, September 19thpp, 20-22.

Dastan, H., Calmasur, G., & Turkez, H.

2016

Entrepreneurship and its Genetic Basis. *Austin J Mol & Cell Biol*, 3(1), 1007.

Esplen, E., & Brighton Institute of Development Studies. (2009). *Gender and care: overview report*.

Brighton: Institute of Development Studies European Commission. (2008). Evaluation on Policy: Promotion on Women Innovators and Entrepreneurship.

Kanze, D., Huang, L., Conley, M. A., & Higgins, E. T.

2018

We ask men to win and women not to lose: Closing the gender gap in startup funding. *Academy of Management Journal*, 61(2), 586-614.

Pareek, P., & Bagrecha, C.

2017

A thematic analysis of the challenges and work-life balance of women entrepreneurs working in small-scale industries. *Vision*, 21(4), 461-472.

Sima, V., & Gheorghe, I. G.

2017

Women Entrepreneurship in Romania: Evolutions and Challenges. *International Journal of Sustainable Economies Management (IJSEM)*, 6(3), 26-34.

Terjesen, S. A., & Lloyd, A.

2015

The 2015 female entrepreneurship index. *Kelley School of Business Research Paper*, (15-51).

Vera Iurcu

2021,

Fonduri europene 2021: Competiție cu 350.000 euro pentru femei în antreprenoriat, Retrieved from <https://www.startupcafe.ro/fonduri-europene/competitie-femei-antreprenoriat-2021.htm>